

An Interaction Effect of Self and Emotional Intelligence on Academic Achievement of CBSE School Students

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Abstract: *Self is the ability to make a balanced judgment by comprehending the complexity of the task and situation in hand. Emotional Intelligence is the ability to distinguish the problem from a given situation or conditions and to find out ways in which to overcome such situations. Academic achievement is described as performance in the subjects of the curriculum. The present paper is undertaken with a view to study the interaction effect of selected independent variables viz., Self and Emotional intelligence on dependent variable Academic Achievement. The findings of the study revealed that high and low Self, and Emotional Intelligence both influence on academic achievement of students. But Interaction effects of the self and emotional Intelligence do not influence on academic achievement of students. Self is a gestalt which is available to awareness through not necessarily in awareness. Emotional problems are of minor nature but they have potentiality to cause disturbance and deleterious effect on academic achievement. Emotional intelligence enables the students to receive emotions, express emotions and attain emotional knowledge to regulate their emotions reflectively, so as to promote their emotional and intellectual growth. The academic performance of CBSE school students is influenced by both the variables like Self of the students as well as their Emotional Intelligence.*

Keywords: Self, Emotional Intelligence, Academic Achievement, CBSE School

I. Introduction

A great need is felt to infuse the lesson of development of the self among students and their emotional intelligence into the fabric of school life and to investigate the influence of self and emotional intelligence on academic achievement of Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) students. The ability to process one's own self and emotional content influences the individual ability to think, plan ahead and solve problems. Both abilities determine the extent to which the person will use his or her potential abilities to cope up with challenges in life.

CBSE School

The objectives of CBSE are : to define appropriate approaches of academic activities to provide stress free, child-centered and holistic education to all children without compromising on quality ; to analyze and monitor the quality of academic activities by collecting the feedback from different stakeholders ; to develop norms for implementation of various academic activities including quality issues; to control and coordinate the implementation of various academic and training programmes of the Board; to organize academic activities and to supervise other agencies involved in the process ; to adapt and innovate methods to achieve academic excellence in conformity with psychological, pedagogical and social principles ; to encourage schools to document the progress of students in a teacher and student friendly way ; to propose plans to achieve quality

benchmarks in school education consistent with the National goals ; to organize various capacity building and empowerment programmes to update the professional competency of teachers ; to fulfil the educational requirements of those students whose parents were employed in transferable jobs ; to bring innovations in teaching-learning methodologies by devising students friendly and students-centered paradigms ; and to regularly updating the pedagogical skills of the teachers and administrators by conducting in-service training programmes, workshops, faculty development programmes, content enrichment programmes, etc.

The Self

The self is the portion of the phenomenal field gradually becomes differentiated. The self or self-concept denotes, “the organized, consistent conceptual gestalt composed of the perception of the characteristics of the ‘I’ or ‘me’ and the perceptions of the relationships of the ‘I’ or ‘me’ to others and to various aspects of life, together with the values attached to these perceptions. It is a gestalt which is available to awareness through not necessarily in awareness. It is a fluid and changing gestalt, a process, but at any given moment it is a specific entity”. The self is, of course, one of the central constructs in Rogers’ theory, and he has given an interesting account of how this emerges and influences on one’s own personality and behaviour. Research studies have also revealed a positive relationship between the self of an individual and the academic performance.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing one’s own feelings and that of others ; for motivating others, and for managing one’s own emotions well and their relationships. Furthermore, one can describe Emotional Intelligence as the ability to distinguish the problem from a given situation or conditions and to find out the ways in which to overcome such situations.

Though ‘intelligence’ and ‘emotion’ were considered in opposition during earlier days, various contemporary researches done in this area, point to the fact that ‘cognition’ and ‘affect’ are integrated processes – affect influences many aspects of cognitive functioning, including memory, attention and decision making. Theory of Emotional Intelligence also, was developed as the concept of intelligence and broadening it to include an array of mental abilities, including social, practical and personal intelligence. Emotional Intelligence often operates on cognition or information processing that involves matters of personal and emotional importance to individuals and their relationships. Using emotions also involves the ability to harness feelings that assist in certain cognitive enterprises, such as reasoning, problem solving, decision making and interpersonal communications.

Academic Achievement

According to Cosmo Dictionary of Education, “Achievement is a performance in school or college on standardized series of education tests. The term is used more generally to describe performance in the subjects of the curriculum”. Academic achievement can be defined as excellence in all academic disciplines, in class as well as extracurricular activities. It includes excellence in sporting, behaviour, confidence, communication skills, punctuality, assertiveness, arts, culture, and the like.

Based on past literature, there were numerous definitions of academic achievement. However, in the present study academic achievement is defined as a student’s academic performance in school subjects.

II. Review : An Overview

The world is becoming more and more competitive. With the advent of technology and recent globalization, the complexities of life have increased manifold. Quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. Parents desire that their children climb the ladder of performance to as high a level as possible. This desire for a high level of achievement puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, schools, and,

in general, the educational system itself. These environmental pressures require an apt combination of intellectual and emotional wealth to set new standards in teacher education. The teaching profession requires high level of emotional competencies such as rapport, harmony and comfort while dealing with student groups. Large scale reviews of research have consistently shown that emotional and social competences of teachers have an impact on the behaviour of pupils (Weare, 2002). In a classroom situation, children tend to draw a lot from their teachers directly and indirectly. The feelings of the teachers, the way they behave, the way they handle situations, and the way they control their lives is all seen as well as absorbed by students. Therefore the teacher has to be an empathetic person who understands the feelings of students and has competency necessary for good teaching (Olson and Wyett, 2000).

Today, as a result of consumerist and commercial society, the security and warmth of family is lacking. Emotional imbalances i.e. anxiety, tension, frustration and disagreements are becoming the most important hurdle in achievements of pupils. With the influence of western culture, media exposure, easy access through internet and mobile, the children are getting into violence, drug abuse, crime and other related problems. The problem gets more acute in adolescents as adolescence is a period of heightened emotionality and emotional adjustment. Teacher training institutions need to orient the trainees with the stress and emotional demands in the classroom so that they are able to appropriately respond as well as cope with these situations and provide positive learning environment (LoVette, 1997). Emotional Intelligence (EI) of teacher's increases the Achievement Motivation, optimism, joy, and purpose of learning by students while decreasing anxiety, depression and isolation in them.

Research findings have proved that teachers with high Emotional Intelligence are better equipped to keep their students engaged in learning activities. They are able to spend more time with the students monitoring their work. On the other hand, teachers with low Emotional Intelligence lack in perseverance and give negative feedback to students (Gibson and Dembo, 1984). Studies conducted by Woolfolk and Hoy, (1990) on pre-service teacher trainees have indicated that teachers with higher Emotional Intelligence are more humanistic in their approach. Their skills of questioning as well as presenting a lesson are better as compared to those teacher trainees who lack Emotional Intelligence. According to the findings of Emmer and Hickman (1991), emotionally intelligent teachers are more effective in classroom management techniques and are thus fully equipped to deal with difficult situations. Teaching carried out by emotionally matured teachers is more stable than that of emotionally immature or unstable teachers (Bansibihari and Surwade, 2006). Teachers who are emotionally mature are generally self-aware, can make personal decisions and manage their feelings well. They can handle stress, empathize with others, can communicate well and can build trust in others. Emotionally matured teachers have the capacity to recognize their strengths and weakness and can take responsibility for their actions. They can be assertive without being insulting and know when to lead and when to follow. They are effective as leaders and resolve conflicts following win-win model. Thus, emotionally matured teachers can think, feel as well as act better and facilitate learning by the child.

According to Goleman (1995), programme on emotional literacy improves the academic achievement and school performance of children. Emotional Intelligence is an important factor that influences the student's confidence, Self-control, Self-Concept, Achievement Motivation, Academic Achievement and later on professional success. I.Q. is inherent but E.Q. can be developed and nurtured. A teacher with high I.Q. may not necessarily be high on E.Q. Employers of today prefer a person with high E.Q. rather only high I.Q. So, before joining a school, if a teacher comes well equipped with fine emotional skills, while undergoing pre-service training, he/she will not only become a more effective teacher, but, will also be able to handle the daily strife and struggle of life with more ease. The present study adds to the theoretical understanding of the concept of E.Q. as it states the relationship of Emotional Intelligence with Self-concept, Achievement motivation and Academic achievement of Student-teachers.

III. Statement of the Problem

The study was undertaken with a view to study the interaction effect of selected independent variables viz., the Self and Emotional intelligence of CBSE school students on dependent variable Academic Achievement. Thus, the statement of the problem is "*An Interaction Effect of Self and Emotional Intelligence on Academic Achievement of CBSE School Students*".

Variables

Independent Variables

- i. The Self of CBSE School Students
- ii. Emotional Intelligence of CBSE School Students

Dependent Variable

- i. Academic Achievement in CBSE School Subjects

IV. Objectives of the Study

The present study was designed with the following objectives in view :

1. To investigate the main effect of the self on the academic achievement of CBSE school students.
2. To investigate the main effect of emotional intelligence on the academic achievement of CBSE school students.
3. To investigate the interaction effect of the self and emotional intelligence on the academic achievement of CBSE school students.

V. Research Hypotheses

The present study was designed with the following hypotheses in view :

1. Effects of high and low self of CBSE school students differ significantly in terms of their academic achievement.
2. Effects of high and low emotional intelligence of CBSE school students differ significantly in terms of their academic achievement.
3. Interaction effects of self and emotional intelligence of CBSE school students differ significantly in terms of their influence on academic achievement.

VI. Definitions of Technical Terms

The Self

The self is the portion of the phenomenal field gradually becomes differentiated. The self. Self denotes, "the organized, consistent conceptual gestalt compose of perception of the characteristics of the 'I' or 'me' and the perceptions of the relationships of the 'I' or 'me' to others and to various aspects of life, together with the values attached to these perceptions. It is a gestalt which is available to awareness through not necessarily in awareness. It is a fluid and changing gestalt, a process, but at any given moment it is a specific entity". The notion of the self refers to a person's experience as a single, unitary, autonomous being that is

separate from others, experienced with continuity through time and place. The experience of the self includes consciousness of one's satisfaction of physical drives as well as one's inner character and emotional life.

Emotional Intelligence

Various definitions of emotional intelligence were proposed by different psychologists, like Cooper (1996); Bar-On (1997); Mayer and Salovey (1997); Goleman (1998); Freedman *et al.*, (1998); Singh (2003). But the generalized meaning of emotional intelligence which all the definitions supported is, that emotional intelligence is a unitary ability (related to, but independent of standard intelligence) helpful in knowing, feeling and judging emotions in close cooperation with one's thinking process to behave in a proper way, for the ultimate realization of the happiness and welfare of the self in tune with others.

Academic Achievement

Generally speaking academic achievement was defined as "a student's academic performance in school" (Chen 2007). In the current research, Academic Achievement is defined as the scores obtained by VIII and IX standard CBSE school students in the annual examination held during March / April 2019.

CBSE Schools

The Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) is a national level board of education in India for public and private schools, controlled and managed by Union Government of India. CBSE has asked all schools affiliated to follow only NCERT curriculum

VII. Research Design

Research Method

The study was undertaken using a descriptive method which attempts to describe and analyze the present conditions, with a view to have an accurate picture of the present which in turn forms the basis for future planning and policy-making to develop 'the self' and 'emotional intelligence' of the students in CBSE schools and thereby to improve their academic performance.

Sample

The sample for the study was drawn from the CBSE schools located in Dharwad district. The schools were selected using stratified random sampling technique. Stratification was based on gender (boys / girls) and location (urban/ rural). The study involved 10 urban schools and 10 rural CBSE schools. From each school, about 40 – 50 students studying in VIII and IX standard were selected. The total sample of the study consisted of 600 CBSE school students drawn from 20 CBSE schools in Dharwad district.

Tools Used

For the purpose of the present study, the investigator used sevenfold Self and Emotional Intelligence Scale (SEIS) constructed and validated by Sarabjit Kaur (1996). The reliability of SEIS was established by test-retest method. The reliability coefficient between the two sets of scores was found to be 0.91, which is significant at 0.01 level significance. The validity of SEIS was taken into consideration by two ways 'experts opinion' and 'item analysis'. The total scores were classified as two categories : the self scores and emotional intelligence scores.

Collection of Data

The investigator personally visited CBSE schools of Dharwad district with the permission of the heads of the institutions. The students were given necessary instructions about the various instruments and motivated them to respond genuinely to all the items. The tools and personal data sheets were administered. The data on each variable was properly coded for further analysis.

Statistical Technique

The data on each variable was properly coded for further analysis. In pursuance of the Objectives, the 2-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) technique was used. This provided an indication regarding the main effects and interaction effects of the selected independent variables on the dependent variable.

Table-1: Summary Table of ANOVA – Total Sample

Sources of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean of Sum of Squares	F – Ratio	p - Value	Significance
Main Effects						
The Self (S)	1	72386.63	72386.63	8.0116	< 0.05	Yes
Emotional Intelligence (EI)	1	144044.88	144044.88	15.9426	< 0.05	Yes
2-way Interactions						
S X EI	1	11131.95	11131.95	1.2321	> 0.05	NS
Total	563	5287294.15				

NS : Not Significant

Interpretation

Significance of obtained F_A , F_B , and F_{AB} , ratios are determined by referring to Table – F (Garrett) with df 1 (numerator) and 563 (denominator). The corresponding tabled F-ratio for all these factors is 3.89 at 0.05 level.

- (1) The obtained F-ratio in respect of the Factor – A is 8.0116 and the corresponding tabled F-ratio is 3.89. Since the obtained F-ratio is greater than the tabled F-ratio at 0.05 level, the difference is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.
- (2) The obtained F-ratio in respect of the Factor – B is 15.9426 and the corresponding tabled F-ratio is 3.89. Since the obtained F-ratio is greater than the tabled F-ratio at 0.05 level, the difference is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.
- (3) The obtained F-ratio in respect of the Factor – AxB is 1.2321 and the corresponding tabled F – ratio is 3.89. Since the obtained F-ratio is lesser than the tabled F-ratio at 0.05 level, the difference is not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Findings

- (1) There is a significant difference between the effects of high and low the Self in terms of their influence on academic achievement of CBSE school students.
- (2) There is a significant difference between the effects of high and low Emotional Intelligence in terms of their influence on academic achievement of CBSE school students.
- (3) There is no significant difference between the interaction effects of high/low Self and high/low Emotional Intelligence in terms of their influence on academic achievement of CBSE school students.

VIII. Conclusion

Self (High and Low) and Emotional Intelligence (High and Low) influence on academic achievement of CBSE school students. However, the interaction effects of the Self and Emotional Intelligence of students do not influence on their academic achievement of CBSE school students.

IX. Discussion

The emotional intelligence, if instilled at early age, can positively affect the development of children. It can transform them into better persons, by showing respects for other's criticism, opinions and judgments and practicing positive interactions. Emotional intelligence enables the students to receive emotions, express emotions and attain emotional knowledge to regulate their emotions reflectively, so as to promote their emotional and intellectual growth. The persons, who have control over their emotions, don't get angry in stressful situations. Instead, they have a keen ability to decipher a problem and find a solution. They are excellent decision-makers and know when to trust their intuition. Regardless of their strength, however, they are willing to take lessons from the past mistakes and failures. They took criticism positively and they know when to use it to improve their performance. The students with high emotional intelligence quotient are able to regulate their behaviour, are more confident and have a strong sense of self-efficacy and perform better academically.

The self is the one's belief in his or her capacity to take up and complete a course of action required to accomplish a specific task in a particular context. It is the ability to make a balanced judgment by comprehending the complexity of the task and situation in hand. Greater the self leads to a positive approach to view the problems as opportunities rather than obstacles. Low level of the self decreases the motivation, resulting in less involvement in the work which may inculcate a defeatist attitude and leads towards poor learning outcomes. Students with a strong sense of self believe in change, and are receptive to newer concepts, thoughts and techniques. They have the ability to plan and execute in a better way to fulfil their academic requirements and more willing to experiment with new methods and techniques to meet the needs of their studies.

The high rate of emotional problems in students and average and below average intelligence of students in the present study could be of two main reasons for overall abysmal results in secondary school students as reflected by high failure rates in public examinations. In 2001, the Government of Karnataka was very much concerned about high rate of failure in SSLC examination has proposed to set up a committee to find out reasons for such low success rate.

The message from this finding is that secondary school students need emotional intelligence assistance in schools. This point has been brought out by many earlier researchers (Kapur and Cariyappa 1979, Dhavale, *et al.*, 1979). They have also opined that mental health facilities should be available in schools. They have further highlighted need to sensitize teachers and parents on emotional intelligence aspects. In addition these researchers have outlined difficulties one may encounter in such endeavour.

Educational Implications

The educational implications of the present study are as follows –

- Findings of present study will not only be useful to researchers in terms of future research but shall have important educational implications for policy makers, administrators and teachers who are associated with CBSE schools. This study suggests that personality of students and teachers can be made more effective by developing components of the Self and Emotional Intelligence in them.

- Administrative authorities in educational spheres should facilitate creation of a favourable environment in educational institutions, a functional, attractive and comfortable classroom climate for improvement of teaching –learning conditions. There should be provision of up-to-date and adequate facilities together with provisions for their maintenance.
- Students should be trained with regard to the components of the self and emotional intelligence. They should be guided regarding how to become self-aware i.e. how to recognize the feelings of the moments and use them to guide the decision making. They should be taught how to carry on self-regulation and take up responsibilities, how to handle emotions so that they facilitate rather than interfere with the task at hand. They should be guided regarding self-motivation i.e. how to persevere in face of setbacks and frustrations. They should be provided opportunities for empathizing with others, understanding others feelings and concerns and taking their perspectives. They should be taught how to handle emotions in relationship well and accurately, thereby demonstrating appropriate social skills. The teachers should try to build atmosphere of love and sympathy and try to nurture responsiveness and reciprocity in students in order to develop a positive and high self. They should try to probe the reasons for low achievement level of students and try to eliminate them. Under achievers should be helped both by teachers and parents by boosting their morale and inculcating confidence in them. This will in turn enhance their Emotional Intelligence, which will eventually lead to high Academic Achievement. When student-teachers are trained with regards to these components, it will raise their level of success and performance not only in academics but also in every sphere of life.
- The Curriculum needs re-evaluation to the extent that along with the cognitive, the conative and affective domains of the personality should be taken care of. Administrators and teachers should implement suitable activities in CBSE schools, so as to develop the Self and Emotional Intelligence of the students in proper shape. Efforts should be made to have better interaction between teachers and students so that students receive counseling for personal, emotional and vocational problems. More and More co-curricular activities should be organized in the CBSE schools to give outlet to pent-up emotional feelings of student s.
- Last but not the least, efforts should be made to create congenial environment at home. Healthy family environment promotes emotional stability, social adjustment, personality integration and increased level of Emotional Intelligence of the individual. Extension program for teachers and parents can be planned in a more systematic manner so that this social change process could be cultivated more effectively in the school and in family.

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